

A NOTE ON SOME OF THE ELECTROLYTES OF THE SERUM IN NORMAL INDIANS

BY HEMENDRA NATH CHATTERJEE AND S. SEN.

The following electrolytes have been estimated, *viz.*, sodium, potassium, magnesium and calcium in the blood serum of apparently normal Indians.

The subjects used for observation were adults, of ages varying from 14 to 45 and belonging to both the sexes. The blood was taken on empty stomach between 11-30 a.m. to 12-30 p.m. from the median cubital vein. It will be observed that the figures for calcium are slightly lower and that for magnesium somewhat higher than the figures given by Peters and Van Slyke ("Quantitative Clinical Chemistry," 1932, p. 753) and also by Cameron ("Text Book of Biochemistry", 1933). No appreciable variations were observed due to the difference of sex.

Table I shows the concentrations of sodium, potassium, magnesium and calcium in mg. per 100 c.c. of blood serum.

TABLE I.

Total No. of cases.	30	15	30	30
Male	21	6	23	20
Female	9	9	7	10
	Sodium.	Potassium.	Magnesium.	Calcium.
Highest	378.0	26.0	4.5	12.6
Lowest	289.0	15.0	2.3	7.4
Average	325.0	20.4	3.3	9.5
Mean deviation	± 28.0	± 3.5	± 0.7	± 1.6
Average figure of Hald, Peters and van Slyke (19 cases).	308.0	18.3	2.0	10.0
Average of Cameron per 100 g. of plasma.	150-250	16-22	2.3	10-11
Average figures obtained by other workers.	Rourke (14 cases) 339 mg. per 100 c.c. serum.	Kramer and Tisdall (10 cases) 19.6 mg. per 100 c.c. serum.	Kramer and Tisdall 9.2-10.3; Mukherjee (19 cases) 9.6 per 100 c.c. serum.	

The respective methods that have been used by us are given below :

For sodium we have adopted the method of Dorothy Rourke (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, **78**, 337); for potassium that of Kramer and Tisdall (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, **46**, 339); for magnesium that of Haury's (*J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1938, **23**, 1079) modification of the method of Hirschfelder and Serles (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1934, **104**, 635); for calcium that of Kramer and Tisdall (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, **47**, 75).

Our best thanks are due to Prof. C. C. Basu for his advice, to Drs. S. M. Ghosh and J. K. Sarkar for their assistance.

DEPARTMENT OF PATHOLOGY,
CARMICHAEL MEDICAL COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received March 29, 1940.
